

The Gentleman. A prosocial assistance system to promote considerate driving

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Abstract Supportive and considerate driving is the bedrock of road safety. Unfortunately, considerate driving is not always easy to accomplish in the rush of everyday traffic. Surprisingly, while there are rules, regulations and campaigns to promote considerate driving, the car itself often plays only a minor role. Here safety is considered foremost a matter of caring about the driver and passengers in the car rather than about the more vulnerable cyclists or pedestrians outside the car. To question this, we developed the general idea of *prosocial assistance systems*. These systems create opportunities for drivers to experience prosocial behavior as enjoyable and meaningful. In the present paper, we discuss *The Gentleman*. It supports the driver in giving way to pedestrians even under adverse conditions. We report how we identified giving way as a relevant prosocial practice and present an ideal experience design based on a series of empirical explorations.

Keywords Experience design, Automotive, Prosocial behavior, Considerate driving, Behavior change

Introduction

Paragraph 1 of the German Road Traffic Regulations (StVO) emphasizes that participation in road traffic requires constant cautiousness and courtesy. In addition, every road user is obliged to neither injure, endanger nor impede other traffic members beyond what seems unavoidable. In short: The “ideal” road user is attentive, considerate and supportive towards others, especially the more vulnerable. Of course, reality is different. While traffic becomes more dense at least in Germany (Kraftfahrt-Bundesamt, 2013), hindrances, misunderstandings, and breaches of rules increase, leading to stress, conflict, anger and aggressive driving (Benmimoun, Neunzig, & Maag, 2004; Deffenbacher, Lynch, Filetti, Dahlen, & Oetting, 2003; Galovski, Malta, & Blanchard, 2006; Parkinson, 2001; Shinar, 2007; Shinar & Compton, 2004).

Since attentive, considerate and supportive driving is crucial to road safety, exploring new ways of promoting considerate driving seems important. From a psychological perspective, considerate driving is a form of prosocial behavior. Prosocial behavior circumscribes a “broad range of actions intended to benefit one or more people other than oneself for example behaviors such as helping, comforting, sharing, cooperation, philanthropy” (Batson & Powell, 2003, p. 463). Prosocial driving is defined as “driving behaviors that potentially protect the wellbeing of passengers, other drivers, and pedestrians, and that promote effective cooperation with others in the

driving environment” (Harris et al., 2014, p. 4). In contrast to aggressive driving, only few studies exist in transportation, which focus on prosocial behavior in the broadest sense (e.g., Benmimoun et al., 2004; Ellinghaus, 1986; Ross & Antonowicz, 2004). To promote prosocial behavior in traffic, it seems necessary to make drivers (and others) aware of their own actions and to support the implementation of “better” behaviors (Ellinghaus, 1986, p. 121). In this sense, prosocial driving is an example of designing for change (Hassenzahl & Laschke, 2015; Tromp, Hekkert, & Verbeek, 2011).

Road users are highly affected by the built environment (e.g., Roessger, Schade, Schlag, & Gehlert, 2011, p. 111). As a consequence, structural changes (e.g., roundabouts, shared spaces) are the major tactic to instill considerate driving. However, the car as a platform for interventions is promising, too. It offers a wide range of opportunities to provide feedback to the driver and to suggest alternative, more prosocial courses of action. Quite contrary to this, contemporary car design focuses on the driver and the passengers, their space and safety, and follows an aggressive, individualistic ideal (Redshaw, 2011).

To counteract this, we propose the notion of *prosocial assistance systems*. Similarly to well-known assistance systems designed for the driver's safety and comfort, we suggest to explore assistance aimed at helping the driver to act more considerate, fair and supportive. A

Figure 1. Initial exploration.

first example of this is the *Alliance of the Last Gentlemen* (Knobel et al., 2013). It encourages prosocial driving by suggesting potential ways of behaving (e.g., giving way), activating related norms (e.g., become a role model, one of the last gentlemen on the road) and providing positive feedback, if acts of considerate driving are performed. Another example is *HörMal* (Eckoldt et al., 2015), a system to increase the driver's attention and to activate relevant norms by augmenting the often overlooked German traffic sign "Attention: Children" (i.e., school zones) with the sound of playing children rendered through the car's audio system.

In the present paper, we explore the idea of prosocial assistance further through *The Gentleman*. This is a conceptual design, which assists drivers in giving way to pedestrians under adverse conditions. We describe our inspiration, report the empirical exploration of a minimal prototype, and present an ideal interaction. Note that the name *Gentleman* is not a thoughtless reference to gendered stereotypes about helping behavior. Aggressive driving is a rather male phenomenon (Shinar & Compton, 2004). In this respect, the *Gentleman's* intention is to playfully appeal to the self-image of particular male drivers. In addition, there is a strong asymmetry in the vulnerability of people inside and outside cars, which creates a striking imbalance of power. The *Gentleman* connotes a particular idea of prosocial behavior, namely the gentleman-like forgoing of a right from a position of strength. This also applies to women drivers, since it is more about an imbalance of power among drivers and pedestrians than about an imbalance of power among women and men.

Being a gentleman driver by giving way to pedestrians

Identifying prosocial practices in traffic

While the notion of prosocial assistance implies that people need support in behaving considerately in traffic, prosocial behavior should not be enforced, but rather framed as an opportunity to experience an enjoyable and meaningful moment in everyday life (Hassenzahl, 2010; Hassenzahl et al., 2013).

A first step was to collect individual experiences of prosocial practices in traffic. In an online study, we asked 109 participants (72% female, age: M=30, min=18, max=59) to describe positive or negative prosocial moments in traffic – either from the perspective of a "giver" or "receiver". We collected forty-five positive experiences and used them as inspiration. One experience mentioned repeatedly by both, driver (giver) and pedestrian (receiver), was to allow pedestrians to safely cross the road by slowing down or stopping.

Understanding the practice of giving way to pedestrians

Based on the collected anecdotes, we distilled an essence of this positive and meaningful moment and transformed it into an "experience pattern" (Hassenzahl et al., 2013) – a blueprint of an "ideal" way of letting pedestrians cross the road. To support this, we conducted a first exploration (see Figure 1). We accompanied three participants in their cars (two women age of 34 [X1] and 30 [X2] years and a man age of 31 [X3], all participants held a driving license for at least 12 years). Without detailed information about the focus of the exploration, the participants were instructed to drive several times along a shopping

street during business hours. Here, crossing pedestrians are common. Besides observing the driver's and pedestrians' actions, we carried out a semi-structured, narrative interview with the drivers during and after the trip. The aim was to get a detailed impression of the interaction between driver and pedestrian (e.g., gestures, timing) as well as a notion of what distinguishes enjoyable and meaningful instances of letting a pedestrian cross from the less satisfactory.

Altogether, we observed 14 spontaneous instances of letting pedestrians cross the road. These revealed certain key elements. First, of course, the driver needs to notice the pedestrian's intention to cross the road. The starting point of their "dialogue" is the moment the pedestrian turns towards the lane and notices the approaching car. If the driver is willing to yield to the pedestrian, she reduces speed until the car comes to a stop in front of the pedestrian. Ideally, the speed reduction is done in a way that can be clearly interpreted. If so, the pedestrian understands it as a permission to cross the road. In many cases, the pedestrian then seeks eye contact and the driver clarifies his intention through a hand gesture. Typically, the driver points her hand at the pedestrian and subsequently performs a movement to the other side of the road. The pedestrian responds by raising a hand or giving a nod before crossing the road. This is not only a gesture of affirmation but also gratitude, which seems especially important in this situation. As one driver remarked: *"I really like the situation when the pedestrian recognizes my intention and honors it with a gesture. Because in some way, I want to receive gratitude for it"* (X1). The driver continues her journey, when the pedestrian has cleared the area in front of her vehicle.

In sum, letting a pedestrian pass is a social exchange (Smith, Mackie, & Claypool, 2014) between the driver and the pedestrian. The driver offers a benefit to the pedestrian, who in turn provides a positive feedback (i.e., a "thank you") as an affective reward to satisfy implicit notions of reciprocity. For the driver, a satisfying transaction reinforces the considerate practice (Knobel et al., 2013). To run smoothly, this requires being able to communicate nonverbally. While communication at daytime is at least in principle possible, twilight or darkness creates numerous difficulties. Blinding headlights hamper the pedestrians' ability to make eye contact and to recognize the gestures of drivers in the dark interiors of their cars. Other typical communication "tools" already available, such as headlight flashing and horn signals are ambiguous or have negative connotations. For example, flashing the headlights as prompt to cross the road can be perceived as impatience of the driver leading to the impression of being rushed. In addition, pedestrians perceive the expressive design of many cars combined with bright headlights as aggressive (Bayley, Curtis, Lupton, & Wright, 2005). While a smiling driver politely gestures to prompt the pedestrian to cross the road, her car tells the opposite story through its design. All this leads to miscommunication and ambiguity. In addition, even after having safely crossed the street, the lack of eye

contact and direct communication creates difficulties in expressing gratitude. All in all, this may lead to a quite unsatisfactory experience, despite best intentions.

A minimal prototype to improve giving way under adverse conditions

We created a minimal prototype to further explore the general idea of the *Gentleman*. It had two features. In the dark, the car's appearance is largely determined by its headlights. Thus, when the driver decided to give way to a participant and was already slowing down, we automatically switched to parking lights. This was to clearly communicate the driver's intention to the pedestrian and to create a feeling of safety by letting the car appear more passive. It also initiated the dialogue between both. In addition, the driver was illuminated by an additional interior light located in the sun visor above the driver's head. This is an important precondition for disambiguating the situation through hand gestures and eye contact as well as for facilitating the social exchange. We carried out an exploration of our minimal prototype. An examiner sitting in the back seat of the car simulated the functionality of the "system". The headlights were dimmed the moment the driver started to slow down and the additional lighting was activated when the driver made a gesture towards the pedestrian.

Four people explored the prototype (two women aged 44 [P1] and 43 [P2]; two men aged 30 [P3] and 34 [P4]). All participants held their driving license for at least 12 years and possessed their own car. The set-up can be best described as role play in the field with uninitiated lay participants. In each case the role play was performed with two of the participants and took place after sunset (the earliest was at 9:30pm in the month of July, 2013). Each participant played both, the role of the driver and the pedestrian. The role was determined randomly at the beginning of every new trial.

We specified a circular route through the city to guarantee multiple encounters between "driver" and "pedestrian". The pedestrian was asked to cross the road at the same spot each time (see Figure 2). This gave both, the pedestrian and the driver, the opportunity to get used to the prototype and the situation created through it. After at least six encounters the driver and the pedestrian switched roles. The entire trip was recorded on video from various angles both inside and outside the car. During and after the exploration, we conducted half-structured, narrative interviews, focusing on individual experience and meaning.

What was noticed first was the unusual response of the headlights. One participant in the role of the "driver" said: *"At the beginning, I found it very confusing that the headlights were turned off. And then I couldn't see the pedestrian anymore"* (P1). Another said: *"Suddenly the lights went out. Well, now he can see me, but I see just nothing. But I'm still on the road. I still want to be able to see and to know that everything is all right in front of the car"* (P4).

Figure 2. An empirical exploration of a minimal prototype.

Obviously, drivers were confused when the headlights automatically switched to low beam without warning. They found the resulting poorer light condition disconcerting. Now pedestrians and the area in front of the car were significantly less visible. For the driver, it was as if the headlights had been switched off. This gave rise to an unsettling sense of not being in control of the situation.

For the pedestrians, on the other hand, dimming the headlights was a clear signal. One remarked: “[...] the light goes out, the car goes into a passive state [...] It appears as if the engine stops. Almost. And if the engine has stopped, one can safely cross the street. This makes it clearer” (P4). Another said: “[...] because dimming the lights implies, that the car parks. Or at least implies the intention not to drive for a while” (P2). The parking lights let the car appear more passive, less aggressive, and therefore less dangerous. “This provides a moment of calmness. It gives me time. [...] A signal to smoothly cross the street. This settles the situation” (P2). The passivity created room for a dialogue and reduced the pressure on the pedestrian to cross the street quickly. A “driver” said: “This allows for communication with the pedestrian. It is courteous. I am in fact provided with the right of way” (P4). Through this, the driver was perceived as considerate and courteous.

Over the course of the exploration, the drivers became aware of the value of this gesture for the pedestrian. This even helped them to accept the disadvantage of the poorer light conditions: “I find it somewhat too dark, [...] but now I can signal that he can go. He sees that I get slower. This appears as if I would park. And now he knows, that he can go” (P3). Another

participant said: “It is uncommon because normally the headlights stay on. But after the second or third time it became normal” (P1).

Other than switching the headlights to low beam, which happened “automatically”, the interior communication light was activated when the driver made a hand gesture of “giving way”. Spontaneously, however, this gesture was made only by two participants. The other participants either flashed their headlights to signal to the pedestrian or made no gesture at all and simply waited for the pedestrian to cross the street. During the exploration, participants were then explicitly instructed to use the hand gesture. One “driver” explained: “I saw him standing there, slowed down. I waited to see whether he would go [...] when he didn’t go ... simply made an additional hand gesture and that [...] apparently [...] activated the light and he seemed to see the hand gesture. Or saw it more clearly. [He] was ascertained and crossed the street” (P4).

During the last three rounds, all participants experienced the effectiveness of the “interior communication light”. The pedestrians responded to the drivers’ hand gestures by nodding briefly or waving an arm in thanks. From the driver’s perspective, all participants noted that the “interior communication light” improved communication with the pedestrians and made it more explicit. It made drivers feel confident about being able to signal clearly to the pedestrians that they can cross the street safely. This was also experienced by the pedestrians. One pedestrian said: “It provides a feeling of safety, because you can see the driver” (P3). Or: “It is a courteous gesture somehow. Because it clearly says: ‘Ok, you can cross here now’” (P4). All this clearly disambiguated the situation: “Yes all is clearer. It is more obvious [for the pedestrian] [the concept] enables a better communication” (P1). Or: “I found the situation comforting. You do not need to do more, the pedestrian is aware that I stop. And knows, that I recognize him and give him all the time he needs to cross the street” (P2). “Lighting up the interior, for me is a kind of polite gesture. Because it is a way to reveal yourself. To step out of your anonymity. It is like making a step towards the pedestrian” (P4).

Note that one participant (P2) also expressed concerns about becoming exposed: “I ask myself, do I want the car to act like this? That people can see that I am alone in my car. That I am traveling on my own. [...] The darkness in the interior gives me a sense of security” (P2).

From a driver’s perspective *The Gentleman* definitely improved the interaction with the pedestrian. It provided clear signals about intentions and facilitated more direct communication through eye contact and gestures. However, switching to parking lights was not the solution. It appeared to the drivers as if switching the headlights off entirely. From a pedestrian’s perspective, the encounter with the car appeared less dangerous through the concept. The dimming of the headlights was perceived as a sign of passivity. Pedestrians can cross the street safe and unhurried.

Figure 3. Storyboard of the ideal interaction .

This sense of safety was further enhanced by the interior light, which enabled the pedestrian to better interpret the driver's intention, allowed for more communication, and reduced anonymity – all viewed as quite a courteous. In sum, all participants (in both roles, driver and pedestrian) experienced the concept positively. It disambiguated and relaxed the situation and provided a courteous feeling and a sense of safety.

The Gentleman – an ideal interaction

Our exploration became the basis for the design of a more refined, ideal interaction. The key challenge was to create a lighting, which lets the car appear more passive and inviting from the pedestrian's perspective,

but at the same time creates good visibility from the driver's perspective.

Figure 3 summarizes *The Gentleman* in a storyboard. The driver recognizes a pedestrian and intends to give way (Scene A). While slowing down, the headlights are lowered to create a deferential impression and to mitigate the danger and aggressiveness of contemporary exterior car design (B). This will also signal the driver's intention to stop for the pedestrian by dipping the headlights already with the beginning of braking. Upon stopping, the dipped headlights become indirect lights to illuminate the surrounding and the road in front of the car, creating the

Figure 4. The F015 Concept Car from Mercedes Benz, Las Vegas, January 2015.

impression of a path for the pedestrian. This inviting path, however, stops at the left, since the driver cannot take the responsibility for parts of the road not in front of the own car. The moment the car comes to a full stop, a special interior light illuminates the driver's face (C). An indirect light illuminates the pedestrians' face without blinding her. This facilitates eye contact and communication through gestures. As already said before, this is not only important for disambiguating the situation, but also for clearly expressing gratitude, which seems crucial for the driver to experience the social exchange as satisfactory (D). The pedestrian crosses the street, paying attention to the oncoming traffic or other cars attempting to overtake the vehicle (E). As soon as the driver continues the journey, headlights revert to normal and the interior light is switched-off (F).

Summary and conclusion

The Gentleman is an example of what we call a *prosocial assistance system*. Their general idea is to support drivers in being more considerate, attentive and courteous towards other traffic members. To this end, we identified giving way to pedestrians as one already existing and potentially suitable practice. *The Gentleman's* aim is to improve the direct communication between driver and pedestrian even under adverse conditions (i.e., in twilight, darkness). An initial exploratory study, which simulated key aspects of the concept, showed that *The Gentleman* is able to improve the communication between drivers and pedestrians with minimum means. Pedestrians as well as drivers perceived the situation created through *The Gentlemen* as meaningful. From the pedestrian's point of view the car becomes more passive and less dangerous. The visual contact enables the pedestrian to more clearly understand the driver's intention. Consequently, the concept creates a feeling of safety,

which is attributed to the driver/car and perceived as courteous. From the driver's point of view, participants understood *The Gentleman* as a designed opportunity to behave courteously. It assists by clarifying intentions and the situation, as well as creating more face-to-face-like contact with the pedestrian, thereby intensifying the encounter. A next step would be to transfer the ideal interaction design into a tangible prototype and develop it through further studies.

The Gentleman as well as the explorations described in this paper were carried out in summer 2013 in cooperation with BMW research. Interestingly, in January 2015 Mercedes Benz presented the F015 concept car, which – among other features – started to address the topic of clearly giving way to pedestrians by projecting a crosswalk onto the road (see Figure 4). While we are not entirely convinced by projecting an actual crosswalk onto the street, since the driver or the car can never take responsibility for a second lane and, thus, the crosswalk metaphor will never fully hold, it is promising that the topic gains some broader recognition by car manufacturers. Note, however, that the F015 is an autonomous car, and this interaction is not meant as a way to promote prosocial driving and satisfying social exchange on the road, but as a polite gesture of a robotic car. Maybe tellingly, there seems to be higher need to let an autonomous car appear considerate than to provide drivers with tools to become more considerate.

Prosocial assistance systems embody an attentive, considerate, yet helping behavior. They assist the driver in the actual implementation (i.e. the action). Their aim is to relax road traffic and to increase road safety. Prosocial behavior is framed as a potential source of positive and meaningful experiences rather than as an annoying necessity. Current headlight

prototypes and the in-series production of high power headlights show that the realization of *The Gentleman* does not require any additional development of technology. New headlight developments are already called “light-based driver assistance systems” (Amsel, Florissen, & Pietzonka, 2010), which actively assist the driver to avoid dangerous situations. They are able to recognize oncoming cars and cut them out of their cone of light. The basic idea of *prosocial assistance systems* is thus not a technical, but a social innovation. It doesn’t require new vehicle technologies, but rethinking and reframing the “emotional” use of cars. In this sense, the challenge is not to implement *The Gentleman*, but to convince premium car manufacturers to abandon the culture of “aggressive individualism”. This culture is largely based on the implicit assumption that the typical customer would not get excited about “prosocial” driving. However, we do not share this pessimistic view. In our opinion, it is crucial for the automotive industry to face the requirements of social sustainability in addition to the already administered requirements of environmental sustainability. And it is certainly possible for interaction design and experience design to make helping others enjoyable.

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